

Potentiometric Studies on Lanthanide(III) Mixed-ligand Complexes in Aqueous Solution

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Several mixed ligand complexing systems of the type 1 : 1 : 1 MAB (where M=La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III}; A=disodium salt of ethyleneglycol bis(2-aminoethylether)tetraacetic acid (EGTA), B=alanine or phenylalanine) have been studied potentiometrically. Thermodynamic equilibrium constants have been evaluated along with the parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° .

THE tendency of the rare earths to form stable mixed ligand chelates by expanding their coordination sphere is reported in literature¹. Ethyleneglycol bis(2-aminoethylether)tetraacetic acid (H₄EGTA), an octadentate chelating agent, forms stable 1 : 1 complexes with lanthanide metal ions². The formation of mixed ligand complex was doubtful³ because of steric hindrance created by the bulky EGTA molecule. However, recent reports^{4,5} on the formation of some mixed ligand complexes of lanthanide metal ions with EGTA as primary ligand, prompted us to investigate few such equilibria. The present communication deals with the results obtained by carrying detailed equilibrium study on 1 : 1 : 1 lanthanide(III)-EGTA-alanine/phenylalanine systems.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and the solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water. Stock solutions of the secondary ligands (HB) were prepared. A solution of disodium salt Na₂H₂EGTA, (H₂A²⁻) was prepared by dissolving the acid (H₄EGTA) in two equivalents of standard NaOH solution. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared and standardised⁶.

The pH-titrations were made with an Elico LI-120 pH-meter in conjunction with glass (EN-66) and calomel (ER-70) electrodes.

Following sets of titrations were performed under nitrogen atmosphere against 0.10 M NaOH at three different ionic strengths ($\mu=0.01, 0.05$ and $0.1 M$; NaNO₃) and at temperatures 25, 35 and 45°, and the total volume in each set was kept at 50 ml : (i) HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), (ii) HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand A ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), (iii) HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand A ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal ion ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), (iv) HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand B ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), (v) HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand B ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal ion ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), (vi) HNO₃ ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand A ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + ligand B ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal ion ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$).

Results and Discussion

Algebraic method of Martell and Chaberek⁷ as modified by Dey *et al.*⁸ has been used to obtain the values of the dissociation constants of the various ligands and the stability constants of 1 : 1 binary and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes.

Formation of mixed ligand complex is evidenced by the comparison of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand titration curve with the theoretical composite curve⁹. It is observed that the former runs superimposed on the latter upto $a=2$, pH ≈ 7.1 (where a is the moles of alkali per mole of metal ion in 1 : 1 : 1 MAB system), which suggests the non-interaction of secondary ligand upto this stage. However, at $a > 2$, the experimental curve is displaced from the composite curve, providing evidence for the increased interaction in presence of two ligands, thereby suggesting the formation of ternary complex through stepwise equilibria. The occurrence of precipitate in 1 : 1 Ln(III)-alanine and Ln(III)-phenylalanine systems at pH ≈ 7.8 , but the non-appearance of any solid phase in ternary systems further supports the formation of mixed ligand complex in solution.

In the solution following equilibria is expected to exist :

Hence at any pH in mixed ligand system,

$$C_M = [M^{3+}] + [MA^-] + [MB^{2+}] + [MAB^{2-}] \quad (1)$$

$$C_A = [H_2A^{2-}] + [HA^{3-}] + [A^{4-}] + [MA^-] + [MAB^{2-}] \quad (2)$$

$$C_B = [HB] + [B^-] + [MB^{2+}] + [MAB^{2-}] \quad (3)$$

where, $C_A = C_B = C_M$.

From mass balance,

$$aC_M = [HA^{3-}] + 2[A^{4-}] + 2[MA^-] + [B^-] + [MB^{2+}] + 3[MAB^{2-}] \quad (4)$$

where, a is the moles of alkali per mole of metal ion in 1 : 1 : 1 MAB system.

From equations (1), (2), (3) and (4) and by introducing the dissociation constants of the ligands we have

$$C_M(3-a) = a_1[A^{4-}] + b_1[B^-] \quad (5)$$

where, $a_1 = \frac{2[H^+]^2}{K_1^A K_2^A} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_3^A}$

and $b_1 = \frac{[H^+]}{K_1^B}$

Further,

$$C_M - C_A = [M^{3+}] + [MB^{2+}] - [H_2A^{2-}] - [HA^{3-}] - [A^{4-}] = 0 \quad (6)$$

and

$$C_M - C_B = [M^{3+}] + [MA^-] - [HB] - [B^-] = 0 \quad (7)$$

Introducing the dissociation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of the binary complexes, equations (6) and (7) respectively can be written as

$$[M^{3+}]\{1 + K_{MB}[B^-]\} = a_2[A^{4-}] \quad (8)$$

and

$$[M^{3+}]\{1 + K_{MA}[A^{4-}]\} = b_2[B^-] \quad (9)$$

where, $a_2 = \left(\frac{[H^+]^2}{K_1^A K_2^A} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_3^A} + 1 \right)$ and $b_2 = \frac{[H^+]}{K_1^B}$

Equating (8) and (9) and then putting the value of $[B^-]$ from equation (9) we obtain,

$$[A^{4-}]^2 (a_2 K_{MA} - b_2 d^2 K_{MB}) + [A^{4-}] (a_2 + db_2 + 2e_1 db_2 K_{MB}) - (b_2 e_1 + b_2 e_1^2 K_{MB}) = 0 \quad (10)$$

where, $e_1 = \frac{(3-a)C_M}{b_1}$ and $d = \frac{a_1}{b_1}$

Solving the quadratic equation (10), the value of $[A^{4-}]$ was obtained. Only the positive roots of equation (10) were considered. The value of $[B^-]$ was then calculated from equation (9). The concentration of the free metal ion at different pH was calculated using equation (8) or (9). The concentration of MA^- and MB^{2+} species were obtained with help of following expressions using their formation constants of binary species,

$$[MA^-] = K_{MA}[M^{3+}][A^{4-}]$$

and

$$[MB^{2+}] = K_{MB}[M^{3+}][B^-]$$

Finally the concentration of the mixed ligand species MAB^{2-} over the entire pH range, was calculated

from equation (1) by substituting the values C_M , $[M^{3+}]$, $[MA^-]$ and $[MB^{2+}]$.

Analysis of mixed ligand titration data between $a=0$ and 3, from pH ≈ 3.5 to ≈ 10.0 on the above grounds, gave the concentration of various complex species and free metal ion at different pH. Plot of percentage distribution of metal ion among various complex species as a function of pH are given in Fig. 1. It is observed that upto pH ≈ 7.8 , no mixed ligand species is formed. It is clearly evident

Fig. 1. Distribution % of M in various metal complex species in 1:1:1 MAB system: M=La(III), A=EGTA, B=alanine (—) or phenylalanine (---).

that the pH from which formation of MAB^{2-} complex starts, about 99% of total metal ion exists as MA^{2-} complex. Thus the relevant equilibrium for mixed ligand complex formation reaction is

The trends observed for the values of the dissociation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of the metal complexes at different ionic strengths are agreement with the earlier observations¹⁰. With increasing temperature, stability constants show a decreasing trend (Table 1). The parameters ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 are calculated (Table 2).

From the high values of the stability constant obtained for 1 : 1 (Ln-EGTA)⁻ chelates, it is likely that all the eight coordinating positions of EGTA are attached to Ln^{III} ion which is consistent with the earlier results⁵. The attachment of the secondary ligand would therefore necessitate further expansion of the coordination number of Ln^{III}. However, the formation constant values of mixed ligand complexes which are relatively low, does not favour

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS* OF PROTON-LIGAND, METAL-LIGAND AND MIXED LIGAND SYSTEMS

Parameter	Ln(III)-EGTA-Alanine			Ln(III)-EGTA-Phenylalanine			
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	
-log K_A	8.87	8.62	8.52	8.87	8.62	8.52	
-log K_A^A	10.47	10.29	10.10	10.47	10.29	10.10	
-log K_B^B	9.81	9.73	9.60	9.40	9.29	9.09	
log K_{MA}^1	La	15.31	15.20	15.09	15.31	15.20	15.09
	Pr	15.86	15.74	15.66	15.86	15.74	15.66
	Nd	16.06	16.00	15.43	16.06	16.00	15.13
	Sm	16.45	16.29	16.20	16.45	16.29	16.20
log K_{MB}	La	4.32	4.22	4.12	4.01	3.90	3.79
	Pr	4.93	4.81	4.70	4.35	4.25	4.11
	Nd	5.16	5.05	4.96	4.59	4.42	4.30
	Sm	5.45	5.32	5.22	4.77	4.65	4.55
log K_{MAB}	La	2.52	2.40	2.32	2.50	2.39	2.25
	Pr	3.19	3.01	2.88	2.85	2.70	2.59
	Nd	3.39	3.22	3.10	2.94	2.82	2.69
	Sm	3.58	3.43	3.32	3.07	2.89	2.62

*Obtained by extrapolating the data at three different ionic strengths to zero ionic strengths.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR MIXED LIGAND SYSTEMS

Parameter	Ln(III)-EGTA-Alanine			Ln(III)-EGTA-Phenylalanine			
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	
- ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	La	14.30	14.09	14.05	14.18	14.01	13.63
	Pr	16.11	17.65	17.46	16.18	15.85	15.68
	Nd	19.24	18.90	18.78	16.69	16.56	16.31
	Sm	20.32	20.12	20.12	17.44	16.97	17.06
- ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	La	—	20.99	29.86	—	19.24	26.14
	Pr	—	31.49	24.28	—	26.22	20.53
	Nd	—	29.77	22.37	—	20.99	24.26
	Sm	—	26.22	20.53	—	31.51	31.74
- ΔS° (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	La	—	22.40	49.71	—	16.98	39.33
	Pr	—	44.93	21.44	—	33.66	15.25
	Nd	—	35.19	11.28	—	14.38	25.00
	Sm	—	19.80	1.28	—	47.20	46.16

the view of expansion of the coordination number. Formation of mixed ligand complex may thus be

interpreted as involving the displacement of some of the carboxylate groups of EGTA to accommodate the second ligand. This view is further supported by the fact that mixed ligand complex formation is observed in Cu-EGTA-alanine and Cu-EGTA-phenylalanine systems and the magnitude of the stability constant of ternary chelates of copper(II) are almost similar to that of Ln(III)¹¹, which suggests a similar type of coordination. If the formation of mixed chelate with rare earths were due to expansion of the coordination sphere, it would be reasonable to expect that no mixed chelate would be formed with Cu^{II}, since this ion is not reported to show a tendency for the expansion of the coordination sphere. The order of stabilities of the various metal complex species formed is La^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III}.

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